

Linguistics and Medicine

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Abstract. *The article describes the relationship between medicine and linguistics, and describes such fields as medical linguistics, neurolinguistics, psycholinguistics, which were formed as a result of the integration of these two sciences. In addition, the development of medical linguistics formed in the field of medicine and linguistics is discussed, and the linguopoetic aspects of lexemes used in medical poetry are discussed.*

Key words: *History of medicine, medical linguistics, medical poetry, poetry therapy, music therapy, medical units, medicine and folk-talk.*

The history of medicine is the same as the history of mankind. The reason we say this is that people who lived a few thousand years ago fought for their health and developed the first medical skills. It is a confirmation of our word that some treatment methods, descriptions of medicinal substances and names of 100 medicinal plants are mentioned even in the ancient book—"Avesta". Linguistics and medicine have been ancient companions of people. Because, since the early times, people have communicated with each other through the exchange of different signs of information, or pictorial information (pictographic) and language, that is, in linguistic collaboration, they felt the need for medicine to treat their body[1]. It appears that medicine and linguistics have been considered related from ancient times.

In today's era of globalization, along with many other sciences, a number of achievements have been made in the field of linguistics. In particular, many field linguistics have been formed and developed. As a result of integration between sciences, various new theories were created and emerged in the field of science. The formation of medical linguistics on the basis of the combination of linguistics and medicine and the creation of a number of field dictionaries in its bosom served many medical workers and patients. Another achievement of medical linguistics is "poetry therapy" in medical poetry. Poetry has been coming soon to the human soul since classical times. This is why poetry and poetry were developed widely in the cultures of different nations. Ibn Sina was one of the scholars who described medicine in the literature of the eastern people in urjuza (poetic epics) and had a great influence on the work of poets and physicians after him. In addition to his urjuzas in Arabic, he also expressed his thoughts on medicine in Persian ghazals, qitas, and rubai. In addition, we can find examples of poetic medicine in the works of Abu Rayhan Beruni, Khusrav Dehlavi, Saadi Sherozi, Abdurahman Jami, Alisher Navoi[2]. The development of language also affects medicine. Including language development or the influence of various external factors enriches language terminology and medical terminology with new words. Looking at the history of medicine, as a result of the rapid development of trade and cultural relations of the peoples of Central Asia with the near and far countries, great changes have taken place in the form and content of medical terminology. Practitioners of folk medicine have developed new treatments based on natural philosophy by balancing the four main fluids in the body. Owners of this profession are called "doctors". New treatments have led to the differentiation of professional names. For example, it was invented to treat diseases with the help of music and melody, and the doctors involved in music therapy were called

"composers". In their performances, music is also divided into cold, hot, dry and wet qualities[3]. In the Middle Ages, the conquest of Central Asia by the Arabs opened the way for the activity of physicians working in the Islamic direction. Azaimkhan, Alaschi, Akhun, Wali, Dervish, Duokhan, Eshon, Qalandar, Kinnachi, Kuf-Sufchi, Mashaikh, Mullah, Murid, Pir, Said, Sufi, Shaykh and others appeared in the medical terminology. According to these doctors, illness is a punishment for sins, a test sent to man by God. Many scientists who made a great contribution to the development of world science and culture: historians, mathematicians, geographers, botanists, astronomers and artists, along with great doctors who played a major role in the development of medicine: ar-Razi (Razes), Ibn Sina (Avicenna), Ismail Djurjani (12th century) and others came out. "Devonu Lugotit Turk" (1074-1075) compiled by Mahmud Koshgari, which is of great importance in the history of Uzbek lexicography, served to preserve and organize the terminology of this period[4].

We know well that the doctrine of human health is one of the oldest sciences of medicine. The terminological layer of this field includes several hundred thousand words and phrases. The development of the terminological system at the current stage of medicine is a specific reflection of the acceleration and specialization of medical science, which creates the need for a number of new terms. Analysis and study of large medical encyclopedic dictionaries, references, textbooks and other medical materials showed us the existence of a large number, or rather, several tens of thousands of words and phrases - term-metaphors. This clearly demonstrates that one of the most effective mechanisms for the creation of terminological units necessary for the linguistic identification of new facts, processes and concepts that did not exist in medicine, as well as for recording previously accepted ones, is metaphorical nomination.

Medicine is one of the oldest sciences in the world. This is a natural process related to a person's own health and its preservation. The history of the origin, formation and development of medicine as a science ran parallel to the history of the development of the entire humanity. "The Laws of Medicine" is recognized as one of the most important books ever written about medicine. The lexical layer of the work consists mainly of Latin and Greek terms, but there are also Arabic terms, most of which were introduced to science by Abu Ali ibn Sina.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that the commonality of medicine, linguistics and poetry was present in the works of our classical creators, in the wisdom of our great doctors, in the hadiths of our prophet, and since ancient times, while helping our doctors and patients to overcome their diseases, we have brought medical science to mankind in a simple and understandable way.

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